

Point-of-care Ultrasound for Ocular Trauma: A Clear Vision for Rapid Diagnostics

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Learning objectives

The goal of this educational exhibit is to review current literature to provide a structured approach to identifying ocular pathologies in trauma using ultrasonography, for emergency physicians to improve diagnostic accuracy and confidence in managing this subset of presentations.

Background

Ocular trauma is a leading cause of monocular vision loss globally, making it a very common presentation in the Emergency Department (ED). In Australia, there are an estimated to be 20,000 hospitalisations due to ocular injuries annually, all of which require adequate ophthalmological knowledge for timely diagnosis and management¹. Failure to do so may result in ocular impairment which can have significant long-term physical, functional and psychosocial implications. Ultrasonography (USS) or Ultrasound is an excellent tool to assist the emergency physician in their assessment of ocular trauma, not only because of its ease of use and accessibility in the ED, but also due to its high specificity and sensitivity in diagnosing certain pathologies². However, despite these proven benefits, USS and its diagnostic potential are still underutilised in EDs across the country.

Literature findings

Normal anatomy:

From an USS perspective, eye anatomy is described in terms of two cavities - the anterior cavity being structures superficial to the iris and posterior cavity being those deep to it. The most superficial structure seen is the thin convex membrane called the cornea, followed by the anechoic fluid of the anterior chamber. The edges of the eye show echogenic linear bands bilaterally, indicating the iris and ciliary bodies. Below these structures is another convex membrane representing the lens, deep to which is more anechoic space made up of vitreous humour. The posterior concavity of the globe is made up of three layers, namely the sclera, choroid and retina from external to internal of the globe. These layers in the absence of pathology, are difficult to differentiate on USS. Posterior to these layers, the hypoechoic optic nerve can be visualised⁵.

Normal eye ultrasound (Case courtesy of Bruno Di Muzio, Radiopaedia.org, rID: 70415)

Ultrasound Technique:

To perform an ocular ultrasound, patient is to be in a supine position with their eyes closed. Sterile gel is placed on a linear transducer (10-20Hz), and light pressure is applied on the eyelid while being scanned in sagittal and transverse planes⁶. Dynamic eye movements are also assessed to differentiate pathologies which can appear similar on static images.

Anterior Chamber:

- **Traumatic Hyphema:** Hyphema refers to accumulation of blood in the anterior chamber of the eye. Macroscopically visible, although USS will show hyperechoic densities within the anterior chamber⁷.
- **Lens dislocation:** Lens can be visualised more posterior in the vitreous chamber, displaced from its usual position behind the iris⁴.
- **Vitreous Haemorrhage:** Haemorrhage into the vitreous cavity can occur for multiple reasons, although the most common in patients less than 40 years old is blunt or penetrating trauma. Other common causes include proliferative vascular retinopathy, age related macular degeneration and intracranial haemorrhage. An acute vitreous haemorrhage on ocular USS will show multiple echolucent dot-like echoes which represent red blood cells⁸.

Lens dislocated posteriorly into vitreous chamber (Left) (Case courtesy of Maulik S Patel, Radiopaedia.org, rID: 61509) Vitreous haemorrhage (Courtesy of T. Wu, MD, Phoenix, AZ.)

Intraocular Detachments:

- **Retinal detachment:** A retinal detachment is considered an ophthalmologic emergency which may require immediate surgery to prevent irreversible vision loss. As opposed to a normal eye on USS where the retina is almost indistinguishable from the choroid, a part or all the retina is no longer contiguous with the choroid resulting in a distinct hyperechoic line anterior to the choroid, with anechoic vitreous humour in between. This line is usually tethered to the optic disc posteriorly and the ora serrata anteriorly⁹.
- **Posterior Vitreous Detachment:** A vitreous detachment is seen as a thin membrane, which unlike a retinal detachment which is tethered to the optic disc and ora serrata, or a choroid detachment which commence laterally – is a free membrane, crossing over the optic disc, past the ora serrata and has no vascularity on doppler⁵.

Diagrammatic depiction of posterior vitreous detachment to retinal detachment (Source: adapted from Hollands et al., JAMA, 2009)

Complete retinal detachment (Left) - (courtesy of Paul Nyaga Njoroge, Radiopaedia.org, rID: 189736) Posterior vitreous detachment (Right) - (courtesy of Bruno Di Muzio, Radiopaedia.org, rID: 85591))

- **Choroid detachment:** This type of detachment is rare and usually occurs in context of trauma or infection, where space between the sclera and choroid fills with blood or exudate. On USS, it appears as bilateral dome shaped hyperechoic membranes protruding towards the middle from both sides⁵.

Choroid detachment (Case courtesy of Polo, Marcela & Luís, Anna & Segura, Oscar & Bosque, Albert & Appiani, Catalina & Mitjana, Josep. (2016).

Foreign body assessment: Foreign bodies such as metal, glass or wood are echogenic and can be visualised within the globe. However, presence of foreign bodies should raise the suspicion for globe rupture and ocular USS should be discontinued immediately due to risk of worsening the injury though probe pressure. Globe rupture on USS is a heterogenous collection of hematoma, blood and vitreous humour contained within the posterior chamber⁴. Although contraindicated in acute globe rupture, ocular USS is a useful tool to assess for post operative complications after a globe reconstruction¹⁰.

Foreign body in vitreous chamber (Case courtesy of Ammar Haouimi, Radiopaedia.org, rID: 169064)

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